

Copper(II), Nickel(II), Cobalt(II), Manganese(II), Iron(II), Zinc (II), Chromium(III), Oxovanadium(II) and Dioxo-uranium(II) Complexes of 4-Benzoylsemicarbazone-1-phenyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one

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There is an extensive and interesting study on the extraction of metal complexes of 4-benzoyl-1-phenyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one. However, there is no report on the study of metal complexes of the 4-benzoylsemicarbazone-1-phenyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one (BscPMPO) and therefore, we report here the preparation and characterisation of its complexes with Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Fe^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Cr^{3+} , V^{5+} and U^{6+} .

ALL the solvents and reagents used were guaranteed reagents. BscPMPO (m.p. 179°) was prepared by the usual method. Metal nitrates were used in the preparation of Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Cr^{3+} and U^{6+} complexes. Ferrous ammonium sulphate and vanadyl sulphate were used in the preparation of Fe^{2+} and V^{5+} complexes, respectively. In the preparation of all the complexes, the following general procedure was used. A stoichiometric quantities of the hot ethanolic solutions of metal salt and ligand were mixed with continuous stirring. To the resulting solution, sodium acetate (1 g) was added and refluxed for 1 h. The reaction mixture was then concentrated to half of its original volume. The product, thus obtained was then filtered and washed with hot water and finally with ethanol. The product was then dried in air. Aqueous metal solutions were used in the preparation of Fe^{2+} and V^{5+} complexes.

All physicochemical measurements were made as described earlier¹.

Results and Discussion

Elemental analyses (Table 1) indicate metal-ligand ratio of 1:3 for Fe^{2+} and Cr^{3+} complexes and 1:2 for all other complexes. The conductivity measurements suggest non-ionic behaviour of the complexes in ethanol.

The ligand shows bands at 3 000, 3 230 and 3 350 cm^{-1} which may be assigned to the $\nu_{\text{N-H}}$ and $\nu_{\text{O-H}}$. The bands at 1 690, 1 610, 1 585 and 1 210 cm^{-1} may be assigned to amide I (and mainly

due to ring $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$, $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ (azomethine), amide II ($\nu_{\text{C-N}} + \nu_{\text{NH}}$) and amide III (δ_{NH}), respectively³. The infrared spectra of complexes record a downward shift ($\sim 10 \text{ cm}^{-1}$), for the $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ (azomethine) and in some complexes it is further shifted until completely masked by a broad band. This suggests the participation of the azomethine nitrogen in the coordination. All complexes show the absence of amide I, II and III bands and instead show new bands at 1 595 and 1 350 cm^{-1} . They may have their origin in vibration at mode of conjugated C=N-N=C grouping, suggesting destruction of keto group through enolisation^{4, 5} and participation of enolic oxygen in coordination. Infrared spectra of the Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Zn^{2+} and V^{5+} complexes show a broad band in the region 3 500-3 000 cm^{-1} . The broad nature of the band might be due to the mixing up of symmetric and antisymmetric ν_{OH} with that of $\nu_{\text{N-H}}$. This suggests the presence of coordinated water molecules in the complexes. To account for the octahedral stereochemistry for the complexes, association of the two molecules of water might be there. In addition, rocking mode of vibration of coordinated water molecules is observed in the range 780-790 cm^{-1} for all these complexes. A strong and broad band at 945 cm^{-1} observed in the V^{5+} complex may be assigned to the $\nu_{\text{V=O}}$. U^{6+} complex shows a broad band at 910 cm^{-1} which may be ascribed to the asymmetric stretching vibration of linear O-U-O^+ .

The diffuse reflectance spectrum of the Cu^{2+} complex consists of two bands at 14 600 and 20 830 cm^{-1} . Absence of any band below 10 000 cm^{-1} excludes the possibility for the tetra-

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND CONDUCTIVITY DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			Λ_M^* $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$
	M	C	H	
Cu(BscPMPO) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂	8.56 (8.25)	56.70 (56.10)	4.00 (4.90)	5.10
Ni(BscPMPO) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂	7.27 (7.67)	57.10 (56.43)	4.90 (5.00)	2.00
Co(BscPMPO) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂	7.40 (7.70)	57.60 (56.50)	5.70 (5.00)	2.05
Cr(BcPMPO) ₂	5.04 (4.91)	60.50 (61.30)	5.00 (4.80)	1.00
Mn(BscPMPO) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂	7.96 (8.30)	57.00 (56.70)	4.78 (5.00)	8.30
Fe(BscPMPO) ₂	5.10 (5.25)	61.70 (60.96)	4.40 (4.80)	3.55
VO(BscPMPO) ₂ (H ₂ O)	7.31 (6.90)	56.50 (57.10)	4.35 (4.90)	3.46
UO ₂ (BscPMPO) ₂	25.60 (25.30)	46.80 (46.00)	4.25 (3.65)	2.35
Zn(BscPMPO) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂	9.30 (8.40)	56.93 (56.00)	5.27 (4.96)	10.40

*In EtOH.

hedral structure. For the complex with D_{4h} symmetry, following three transitions are possible, ²B_{1g} → ²A_{1g} (ν₁), ²B_{1g} → ²B_{2g} (ν₂) and ²B_{1g} → ²E_g (ν₃). Here, it may be assumed that because of the tetragonal distortion, the energy of the ²B_{2g} state would have been very close to that of the ²A_{1g} and as a result instead of three bands only two bands are observed. An approximate value of 10 Dq (6 275 cm⁻¹) have been determined⁸. The magnetic moment of the complex (2.19 B.M. is in the required range.

The Ni²⁺ complex has a magnetic moment of 3.20 B.M., which is in the range required for six-coordinate spin-free octahedral complex. Its diffuse reflectance spectrum shows bands at 10 989, 16 949 and 23 810 cm⁻¹ which are in the range required for the octahedral structure⁹. Values of B=519 cm⁻¹ have been obtained using diagonal sum rule⁹. β is found to be 0.480. Low values of the B and β suggest the appreciable amount of the covalent character in the metal-ligand bond. The first two bands are broad and unsymmetrical. They also show splitting into two components (ν₁ at 10 989 and 10 416 cm⁻¹; ν₂ at 16 949 and 16 129 cm⁻¹). It is possible to calculate Dt=65 cm⁻¹, Ds=451 cm⁻¹, Dq^{xz}=1 099 cm⁻¹ and Dq^{xy}=984 cm⁻¹ from these splittings. The results suggest the higher field strength in the XY-plane.

The Co²⁺ complex exhibits a broad band around 9 009 cm⁻¹ which may be assigned to the ⁴T_{1g} (F) → ⁴T_{2g} transition (ν₁). The two shoulders at 19 230 and 20 410 cm⁻¹ probably on the tail of the charge transfer band have been observed. The former may be assigned to ⁴T_{1g}(F) → ⁴T_{2g}(P) transition (ν₂) and the latter to the tetragonal distortion¹⁰. Using Ballhausen equation¹¹, 10 Dq=10 140 cm⁻¹, B=757 cm⁻¹ and β=0.676 have

been calculated. The magnetic moment of the Co²⁺ complex (4.43 B.M.) is close to the value required for octahedral structure. However, slightly low value is due to the lower symmetry of the complex.

The diffuse reflectance spectrum of the Mn²⁺ complex shows bands at 12 660, 8 180 and 22 730 cm⁻¹, which suggest hexacoordinated structure for the complex¹². The magnetic moment (5.80 B.M.) of the complex indicates high-spin octahedral environment.

Elemental analysis, magnetic and electronic spectral studies of the Fe²⁺ complex suggest that it has been oxidised to Fe³⁺ during its preparation. The magnetic moment (6.40 B.M.) of the complex is more than a spin-only value, indicating the presence of ferromagnetic impurity in the complex. The bands observed at 18 520, 19 610, 22 220 and 23 280 cm⁻¹ may be assigned to the ⁶A_{1g} → ⁴T_{1g}, ⁶A_{1g} → ⁴T_{2g}, ⁶A_{1g} → ⁴E_g (G), ⁴A_{1g} (G) and ⁶A_{1g} → ⁴T_{2g} (D) transitions, respectively¹³.

Two bands have been observed for the Cr²⁺ complex at 17 860 and 25 970 cm⁻¹. These may be assigned to the ⁴A_{2g} → ⁴T_{2g} and ⁴A_{2g} → ⁴T_{1g} transitions, respectively. The presence of shoulder at 16 950 cm⁻¹ may be due to the lower symmetry of the complex. In tetragonal field, these may be assigned to the ⁴B₁ → ⁴B₂ (17 860 cm⁻¹) and ⁴B₁ → ⁴E (16 950 cm⁻¹) transitions. Using ligand field theory of spin-allowed transitions for octahedral complex, B=853 cm⁻¹ and β=0.927 have been obtained¹⁴. The ⁴B₁ → ⁴B₂ transition equals to 10 Dq^{xy} and the separation energy between ⁴B₁ → ⁴E and ⁴B₁ → ⁴B₂ is (35/4) Dt. Using Dt (104 cm⁻¹) and Dq^{xy} (1 786 cm⁻¹), Dq^z=1 604 cm⁻¹ can be evaluated¹⁵. These values suggest nearly identical

field strength in the XY-plane and along Z-axis. The magnetic moment (3.45 B.M.) of the complex is less than that required for three unpaired electrons¹⁶.

The $V^{IV}O$ complex shows bands at 12 350 and 17 240 cm^{-1} and a weak shoulder at 22 220 cm^{-1} . These may be assigned to ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2E$, ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2B_1$ and ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2A_1$ transitions, respectively. The magnetic moment (2.10 B.M.) is higher than a spin-only value.

The spectra of $U^{VI}O_2$ complex generally show well defined vibronic structure between 21 280 and 30 300 cm^{-1} (Ref. 17). In the present study, the dimagnetic $U^{VI}O_2$ complex shows two bands at 26 315 and 20 000 cm^{-1} . The latter band might be due to metal $\rightarrow$ ligand charge transfer processes¹⁷. The Zn^{II} complex is dimagnetic and may have octahedral structure.

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